

BLOCKCHAIN IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY<https://zenodo.org/10.5281/zenodo.6782920>**Dziatkovskii A.**

*PhD in education (Information Technologies)
Blockchain Technology and Data Science specialist of
PLATINUM SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT COMPANY
Australia*

Abstract

This article examines the development of the digital economy - economy 4.0, in which the key factors and means of production are digital data (binary, information, etc.) and network transactions. Digitalization of the economy allows increasing the efficiency of production and the quality of the resulting products and services. However, the realization of this opportunity is not possible without a change in approaches to management. Relevant is the need for "mobile management (cashless storage, digital transfers), minimum time and money for management without intermediaries, the possibility of independent management regardless of time and location. The article proves that such opportunities as a distributed data registry, all transactions of which are transparent, secure and take place without intermediaries, are provided by blockchain technology. The characteristics of blockchain, the possibility of reducing risks, including fraud, crises, corruption and the negative manifestation of the human factor are considered. The possibilities of blockchain convergence with the practices of scrum, Extreme programming, Feature driven development, Lean Software development, Kanban and others are substantiated. It is concluded that the transfer of governance to blockchain information platforms can completely transform the economy and the market, as all the unique characteristics of resources or objects that are invested in a transaction by each party are converted into digital assets and are clearly recorded by the software code.

Keywords: economy 4.0; digitalization; blockchain; governance.

1. Literature Review
 2. Methods
 3. Results
 4. Discussion
- Conclusion

The digital economy is an opportunity to create digital models of the real world of the economy, which, based on modern technology, will allow the accounting of a variety of resources in the real economy and the processes that occur with these resources. Information technology helps the economy to overcome an eternal drawback - the high level of costs. This factor is critical for some industries in the market. At the moment, for some companies, there is no other way to reduce costs than implementation of IT solutions.

The advantages of the digital economy: increase in labor productivity; simplicity of taxation and control; global automation and standardization of all economic processes: production, educational, medical, social, etc.; reduction of bureaucracy; development of digital money and abandonment of physical means of payment, etc. [4].

The forms of the digital economy depend on the specifics of the countries themselves. In Germany, the focus is on integrating information, communication and manufacturing technologies into smart, self-organizing factories. In the U.S. and China, Industry 4.0 is firmly associated with smart products, Internet platforms and new business models based on them [4].

Three main stages in the development of the digital economy have been identified. The first stage is the development of telecommunications (1900s); computer technology as a mass consumption product (1960s); information technology and information products aimed at the mass consumer market (1980s); the Internet as an

information and communication environment of interaction between subjects of the electronic economy (1990s). The second stage is associated with the creation of the first e-business companies (mid-1990s); the crisis of "overfunding" of EE subjects (2000, USA); formation of international information and communication infrastructure (2000-2005); preparation of technological standards of presence and communication on the Internet (2000); development of electronic payment systems (2000s); convergence of goods and the Internet (since 2005); creation of Internet services (2000s); development of mobile access (since 2005); expansion of the market of mobile and cloud applications (since 2010); preparation for mass use of basic ICT: cloud computing, artificial intelligence, ontology management, blockchain, robotics, big data, etc, the development of markets for household smart technologies based on Internet connections of physical objects (since 2013); the emergence of the electronic finance market (since 2009). The third stage is the formation of a system of new approaches and methodologies in economic management, in fact, we are talking about a revolution in management [6].

The digitalization of the economy is impossible without a change in approaches to its management [1].

Classical management is characterized by a clear planning of tasks and is strictly tied to the time of their implementation. It cannot be used to manage projects, which consist of many subprojects, are inconsistent in execution, require planning, implementation, development and control of the results of all projects simultaneously.

Hence the focus on "mobile management (cashless storage, digital transfers), minimum time and money costs of management without intermediaries, the possibility of independent management regardless of time

and location; the need to reduce risks, including fraud, crises, corruption and the negative manifestation of the human factor [7].

Modern management are the principles of creating a mobile and easily changeable production organization, in contrast to the previous linear management based on the principle of "waterfall" [2]. It uses such practices as scrum, Extreme programming, Feature driven development, Lean Software development, Kanban and others [10]. These agile management methods, based on the iterative and incremental principle, can converge with blockchain technology [5].

One of the main reasons blockchain is so attractive to businesses and other human activities is decentralization and transparency. Blockchain is more than a decentralized network. Unlike a conventional decentralized network, where there are still certain unifying points, blockchain is a distributed registry in which all participants are directly connected to each other [1].

An important issue of governance is fairness and trust. Injustice in the economic system leads to the fact that people do not trust either entrepreneurs or the state. Transferring governance to blockchain information platforms can completely transform the economy and the market, as all the unique characteristics of resources or objects that are invested in a transaction by each party are converted into digital assets and clearly captured by the software code. They become part of a chain of blocks included in a decentralized database. They cannot be fraudulently dealt with, and this "provides an autonomous mode of legal relationship management without the involvement of a third party." [11].

Blockchain has this perspective as a distributed data registry, all transactions of which are transparent, secure and occur without intermediary intervention.

Blockchain, as a distributed decentralized system, provides a high level of security for transactions and storage of funds. Such a system cannot be cheated or destroyed because information is stored by each user [8].

Each transaction is validated by several independent nodes, making it impossible to spoof data or bribe verifiers.

Unlike the local systems used by banks, the exchange of funds using a decentralized system takes much less time and allows for a huge number of transactions in a matter of seconds.

Unlike banking structures, where the speed of transactions depends directly on the workload and the power of the local server, in the blockchain computing power is distributed around the world, and the huge number of participants in the chain provides high power and, consequently, speed [11].

Governments around the world are beginning to implement blockchain technology in public sector management. This reduces economic costs, automates transaction processing, ensures transparency, increases citizen trust, and reduces bureaucracy [9]. Blockchain is a high level of reliability and new opportunities for fast access to necessary data and simultaneous processing of large amounts of information.

Blockchain technology is universal. Its use depends only on the activity and creativity of IT-specialists and the demand in the market.

Blockchain works best in areas where there are many intermediaries. For example, real estate, which traditionally has many third parties and intermediaries. With blockchain, contracts can be checked and applied automatically, without the need for human interaction. This reduces the need for agents, lenders, inspectors, insurance agents [3].

Conclusions

Blockchain is one of the major technologies of the future. Although the technology appeared not so long ago, it has already become popular all over the world. The technology is rapidly developing and being introduced into various spheres of human activity, especially where a large number of participants and a minimum of intermediaries is required. In the future, the Fourth Industrial Revolution will create new technologies that will connect blockchain, artificial intelligence, robotics, Internet of Things, cyber systems, etc. cyber systems, artificial intelligence, big data, paperless technologies, additive technologies (3D printing), cloud and fog computing, unmanned and mobile technologies, biometric technologies, quantum technologies, identification technologies.

REFERENCES:

1. Chakraborty P., Shahriyar R., Iqbal A., Bosu A. Understanding the software development practices of blockchain projects: a survey, in: ESEM 2018, October 11–12, 2018, Oulu, Finland, ACM, 2018.
2. Chohan U. The Problems of Cryptocurrency Thefts and Exchange Shutdowns, Tech. rep., Discussion Paper Series: Notes on the 21 St Century, School of Business and Economics, University of New South Wales, Canberra, 2018.
3. Digital economy report 2021 III Cross-border data flows and development: For whom the data flow. United Nations Publications // https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/der2021_en.pdf
4. Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2021. Shaping Europe's digital future // <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-economy-and-society-index-desi-2021>
5. Destefanis G., Marchesi M., Ortu M. et al. Smart contracts vulnerabilities: a call for blockchain software engineering?, in: 2018 International Workshop on Blockchain Oriented Software Engineering IWBOSE, 2018.
6. G20 Digital Economy Ministerial Conference // http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/science-and-technology/measuring-the-internet_5k9bhk5fzvzx-en
7. Measuring the Digital Economy The 5th IMF Statistical Forum SessionII: Framing the Conceptual Issue Discussion by Vitor Gaspar, Director, Fiscal Affairs Department, IMF November 16, 2017 www.imf.org/en/News/Seminars/Conferences/2017/05/03/5th-statistical-forum
8. Rocha H., Ducasse S. Preliminary steps towards modeling blockchain oriented software, in:

WETSEB 2018-1st International Workshop on Emerging Trends in Software Engineering for Blockchain, 2018.

9. Sharp H., Rogers Y., Preece J. *Interaction Design: beyond Human-Computer Interaction*, fifth ed., John Wiley & Sons, 2019.

10. Schwaber K., Beedle M. *Agile Software Development with Scrum*, Pearson, 2001.

11. Wohrer M., Zdun U. Smart contracts: security patterns in the ethereum ecosystem and solidity, in: *Blockchain Oriented Software Engineering (IWBOSE)*, 2018 International Workshop on, IEEE, 2018, pp. 2–8.

POST-FIRE FOREST RESTORATION FOR THE TROPICS

<https://zenodo.org/10.5281/zenodo.6782928>

Le Viet Vu

*The University of fire prevention and fighting
243 Khuat Duy Tien, Thanh Xuan, 10000, Ha Noi.*

Abstract

Forests play an important role in improving the natural ecological environment, have great effects in responding to and minimizing damage caused by climate change and natural disasters such as floods, landslides, greenhouse gas effects. The impact from forest fires is huge, it directly impacts climate change. Even under normal conditions, the fires have destroyed the vegetation and animals living in the forest, including precious trees and animals that need to be preserved, making their numbers less and less. Putting many organisms on the endangered list, causing biodiversity loss and ecological imbalance. In order to regenerate those forests, in addition to effort and money, it also takes time corresponding to the age of the forest to regenerate and develop the forest as before. Therefore, active efforts are needed to prevent forest fires and effectively restore the affected forests after fires.

Keywords: Forest fire, climate change, forest restoration, tropics.

Introduction

Since the 1980s, severe wildfires have been on the rise globally. In 2015, the occurrence of fires in the Brazilian Amazon increased by 36% compared to 12 years ago [1]. In the same year, the rate of daily emissions from peat fires in Indonesia exceeded the rate of fossil fuel emissions in the United States, causing serious environmental damage and human health problems throughout the Southeast [2]. The 2019-2022 bushfires that occurred in Australia, burning more than 10 million hectares of forest, have shown that the nature of global wildfires is changing, with increasing scale, nature and intensity. Wildfires are responsible for 5–10% of global greenhouse gas emissions [3], of which 84% of total global fire emissions originate in the tropics [4]. Besides their impact on the global carbon cycle, rain-forest fires are detrimental to forest ecosystems and local communities. They not only reduce biomass but also affect species composition, change water and nutrient cycles, increase the risk of flooding and erosion, and threaten local livelihoods by burning farmland, business and home. Additionally, these fires have a devastating impact on local wildlife as animals cannot escape the fires or are threatened by loss of habitat, food, and shelter.

Vietnam is located in the tropics, but the climate of Vietnam is distributed into 3 regions according to the Köppen climate classification with the North having a humid tropical climate. The North consists of 2 seasons: Summer and Winter. The North Central, Central and South Central regions have a tropical monsoon climate, the southernmost regions of Central Vietnam and the South have tropical savanna characteristics. At the same time, because it is located on the Southeast edge

of the Asian mainland, bordering the East Sea (part of the Pacific Ocean), it is directly affected by the trade monsoon climate, which often blows in the regions of the world. low latitude. The South usually has 2 seasons: the rainy season and the dry season. The data of the General Statistics Office of Vietnam show that, in the 10 years of 2009-2018, forest fires have destroyed nearly 22,000 hectares of Vietnam's forests, causing great economic losses to the country. The peak of this period was in 2010, about 6,723 hectares of forest were destroyed by big fire. In 2007, there were 749 forest fires causing damage of 4,188 ha. In recent years, although the area of forest burned has decreased sharply, there are still unexpected and complicated developments that are unpredictable. In 2017, a sharp increase in rainfall made the weather less dry and hot, contributing to reducing the area of forest burned to the lowest level in the past decade, the damage level was only 471.7 hectares, a decrease of about 80 percent. % compared to 2016 (3,320 ha). By 2018, the damage caused by forest fires had increased compared to 2017 (739.1 ha), but in general, the damage was still low compared to other years. However, in the 10 months of 2019, the burned forest area increased to 2.7 thousand hectares, 3.6 times higher than 2018. Especially, in the peak months of the dry and hot season, many areas Vietnam's forests are in the state of warning of the risk of forest fires at level V (extremely dangerous level), the risk of forest fires is very high, causing the Government and ministries and branches to frequently issue urgent notices to forest fire prevention. Faced with this situation, it is necessary to effectively restore post-fire affected forests using a combination of several post-fire rehabil-